

Survey on Circular Economy and ESG Practices in Industry

31 responses

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Section A: General Information

Collects background details about you and your organization. This helps compare responses across industries, regions, and company sizes.

31 responses

Mondelez

Sharad Ojha

Bank

Roamware

National Institute of Technology Jalandhar

Eagle hills

Central Institute of Technology Kokrajhar; Govt. of India; Kokrajhar; Assam

Re-sustainability

Electrocraft

Auto club

RSP

IT Hardware, Software and Services

Pump industry

International Flavors & Fragrances

Wells Fargo

Infosys

Deloitte

MECON Limited

Central Agricultural University Imphal

The University of British Columbia, Vancouver

mjunction services ltd

Coal India Limited

Dormer Pramet

Welltech infotech pvt ltd

MS

Abhishek Sharma

IFF

SUD-Bev Consulting Pvt Ltd

JINDAL STEEL

Iron and Steel Industry

Indian Institute of Management Raipur

2) Sector/Industry

31 responses

3) Country/Region of operation

31 responses

4) Role/Designation of respondent

31 responses

5) Organization size

31 responses

Section B: Awareness & Integration

Assesses the level of awareness and integration of circular economy and ESG principles in your organization's strategy and operations.

6) How familiar are you with the concepts of Circular Economy (CE) and ESG?

31 responses

7) How would you describe the current level of integration between CE practices and ESG strategies in your organization?

31 responses

Section C: Practices & Drivers

Explores the circular economy and ESG practices your organization adopts and the main drivers motivating these efforts.

8) Which CE practices are currently implemented to support ESG goals? (Select all that apply)

31 responses

9) Rank the key drivers for CE-ESG integration in your organization (1 = Most important, 5 = Least important)

Please assign a unique rank to each attribute. No two attributes should have the same rank

Section D: Barriers & Challenges

Identifies the internal and external obstacles your organization faces in adopting CE-ESG practices.

10) What are the main barriers your organization faces in integrating CE and ESG? (Select up to 3)

31 responses

11) How difficult does your organization find it to measure the impact of CE practices on ESG performance?

31 responses

Section E: Stakeholders & Innovation

Examines the role of stakeholders, partnerships, and innovation in advancing circular economy and ESG adoption.

12) Which stakeholder group has the strongest influence on your organization's CE-ESG agenda?

31 responses

13) To what extent are digital technologies (AI, IoT, blockchain, Industry 4.0 tools) being used to support CE-ESG integration?

31 responses

Section F: Comparative & Future Outlook

Captures your views on how CE and ESG compare in importance and priority for future sustainability strategies.

14) How do CE-ESG integration practices differ between developed and emerging economies? (Select all that apply)

31 responses

15) Which policy interventions or strategic changes would most effectively enhance CE-ESG integration in your sector over the next 10 years? (Select up to 3)

31 responses

16) To what extent has your organization experienced positive outcomes from CE-ESG integration?

31 responses

Section G: Organizational Commitment & Reporting

Assesses your organization's maturity, proportion of focus on CE within ESG, and transparency in reporting practices.

17) Which specific positive outcomes have been observed in your organization? (Select all that apply)

31 responses

18) How long has your organization been engaged in sustainability or ESG-related initiatives?

31 responses

19) What proportion of your organization's sustainability efforts are specifically focused on Circular Economy practices?

31 responses

20) Does your organization publicly report on CE-ESG performance (e.g., sustainability reports, integrated reports, SDG alignment)?

31 responses

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